

**CAUSE-EFFECT CONCEPT AND CAUSAL RELATIONSHIPS IN
AZERAIJANI TEXTS**

AZERICE METINLERDE NEDEN-SONUÇ KAVRAMI VE İLİŞKİLERİ

Gunel AKHMEDOVA

Azerbaijan University, Baku, Azerbaijan, E-mail : gunelahmedova.1987@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A concept is an operational unit of memory, mental vocabulary, conceptual system and language of the brain, worldview, quantum of knowledge. A concept is the mental structure of perceived typed fragments of practice, the meaning of which is retained in memory.

Cause and effect is an important unit of human thinking. Cause and effect are a major part of our thinking process. This concept stores information related to cause and effect in a cognitive environment.

The article examines certain aspects of the causal concept of the Azerbaijani people, reflecting the originality of the national culture, national specifics. The internal structure of the causal concept is revealed through the analysis of different levels.

The formation of a cause-and-effect structure in the text is studied at the syntactic level located above deep cognition. At the cognitive level, the formation of relations between cause and effect is observed, this connection, relations arise in conditions of macro-proposition.

KEY WORDS: text, causal concept, causal relationships, conjunctions of reason, mental thinking.

ÖZET

Bir konser, belleğin, zihinsel sözlüğün, kavramsal sistemin ve beyin dilinin, dünya görüşünün, bilgi kuantumunun işleyen bir birimidir. Bir kavram, hafızada saklanan bir anlamı olan, algısal tipleştirilmiş parçalardan oluşan zihinsel bir yapıdır.

Sebeup ve sonuç da insan düşüncesinin önemli bir birimidir. Düşünce sürecimizin büyük bir kısmı sebeup ve sonuçtur. Bu kavram, nedensel bilgiyi bilişsel alanda depolar.

Makalede, Azerbaycan halkının neden-sonuç kavramının ulusal kültürü ve ulusal özellikleri yansıtan bir veya diğer yönleri incelenmektedir. Sebeup-sonuç kavramının iç yapısı, bireysel katmanları analiz etme sürecinde ortaya çıkar.

Metindeki neden-sonuç yapısının oluşumu, derin bilişin üzerinde sözdizimsel düzeyde sunumda incelenir. Bilişsel düzeyde neden-sonuç kavramları arasında bir ilişkinin oluşumu gözlenir, ilişki, ilişki bir makro önerme koşullarında oluşturulur.

ANAHTAR KELİMELER: metin, neden-sonuç kavramı, neden-sonuç ilişkileri, nedensel bağlayıcılar, zihinsel düşünme.

ANNONATION. In the article, based on texts in the Azerbaijani language, the concept of cause and effect is studied as an important unit of human thinking, national culture, as a side that reflects national specifics. The article characterizes the unidirectionality of relations or temporal asymmetry, which give rise to the causality (causality) of the concept. In the text, information relating to cause and effect is factual, conceptual, and subtextual.

The word "reason" is of Arabic origin, its lexical meaning is "an event or condition that causes the occurrence of some other event or condition": What is the reason that we did not come to work? Cause of mistakes. Everything has a reason (1, p. 42 (541 p.)).

The concepts of cause and effect is one of the main fundamental concepts and categories of philosophy. *"The concepts of cause and effect and Causal relationships are a type of universal relations. Under the concept of cause (lat. Causa) is meant such an event as a result of the action of which another event arises, changing it and leading it; and a new event that has arisen is an effect. The relationship between cause and effect is called causality or causal relationship... If a connection with real things is traced, then an event explaining other events can be called a cause, and if we mean the connection and relation of ideas in the process of cognition, it can be called its basis. There is no problem here since this is a completely abstract definition. Serious problems arise when the question arises of what rules can be used to define a principal-based relationship between cause and effect. Various conceptions of causality emerge from the various possible forms of this relationship. The necessary reasons for the effect are the main reasons, because without them there can be no effect (2, p. 55 (499 p.)).*

In philosophy the concepts of cause and effect differ in its factual and empirical aspects. The reason is the one-sided influence of one subject on another. One event (process) is called the cause of another event only if the first gives rise to the second. For example, in the semasiology section of linguistics, the reason for the semantic evolution of a word ... one reason is a change in the meaning of a word. This is called a linguistic and extralinguistic reason. Linguistic is a social cause, and extralinguistic is historical. Linguistic reason: a) the distinctive feature of the different meanings of the word depends on the syntactic constructions (alma yedim, bazardan alma alma! – I ate an apple, do not buy an apple at the market!); b) another distinctive feature of changing the meaning of a word depends on the lexical context.

Social and historical reason: a change in the meaning of the word occurs along with changes in the living conditions of society, with the pace of development of science and technology. For example: note the historical development of the change in the word "revolution". Revolution of 1905, revolutionary change.

Causality is one of the universal, law-governed, relative forms of events. The event arises, develops and collapses. No doubt the reasons for this are being studied by science. The primary and fundamental feature of causality is the occurrence of an event between two events. The concept of causality is based on determinism (on the general dependent conditions of objective events). That is, the definition of the cause, the subordination of the natural course of things to objective reasons and laws. This means that no event in life happens without a reason. The relationships that give rise to the concept of causality are characterized as unidirectional or temporal asymmetry. For example: in a language, a number of analytical verbs (define, cause, help, and others) implement the desired context of the linguistic story. This causality gives rise to characteristic perception. Such a factor of perception makes it possible to mutually determine the circle of understanding of the conceptual and cognitive character at the cognitive level: "delight, happiness, dream, desire, mercy, love, pity" and other concepts. A text as a specific passage of speech, first of all, functions as a specific communicative and informative unit. One of the special features here are constructions expressing cause-and-effect relationships. Normal text contains information related to a specific cause. For example: Uncle Mamedgasan has a big winter house. *Because* in winter a tandir burned in this house, *for this reason* the beams of this house were completely black. It looks like the house is old; because most of the beams bent (J. Mammadguluzadeh).

Thus, the informational load of this text is dominated by causal ideas. These thoughts are unevenly distributed throughout the text. Information related to causal relationships and contained in

the text is factual, conceptual and subtext. All three types are directly related between the passage of text with the content of the reason and the general text. In the first, the author brings to the attention specific information and facts related to the cause. Several reasons may be indicated in the text. For example, the growing influence of the Azerbaijani language in the 19th century is associated with several reasons; firstly, this is a consequence of the special attention to Azerbaijan on the part of the Russian Empire (because, from an economic point of view, Azerbaijan was a very rich, profitable country), secondly, for Russia, the territory of Azerbaijan was an outlet to Turkey, Iran and to the whole Western Asia. Thirdly, "the Azerbaijani language, in comparison with other Turkic languages, occupied an average position and this also applied to the literary Azerbaijani language (especially the written one)" (3, p. 420 (632 p.)).

The conceptual information associated with the cause is characterized by complexity, is directly related to the general idea of the literary work. This information appears in the process of reading the text, at the end of the work it acquires integrity.

The contextual information associated with the cause is revealed in a hidden form. Full disclosure of the reason becomes impossible. The reader of the work perceives information from the context at the level at which he understands this issue.

Analysis of factual materials shows that in the in the process of history, in the modern Azerbaijani language there are a large number of stable syntactic forms with the content of the cause, which are formed, in the majority, with the participation of conjunctions. And this can be explained by the important role of conjunctions in the syntactic structure of the Azerbaijani language.

Due to the fact that the components of the text in comparison with the components of a complex sentence are larger in number and are independent, it becomes necessary to clarify their semantic relations using conjunctions. Each of the sentences that make up the text comes into contact with the sentence with which it is associated with semantic-grammatical relations. And in the grouped polar connections of these components, which give even more extensive information, a special role is played by the conjunctions chosen by us as a cause-and-effect object.

In the Azerbaijani language, cause constructions determine two situations between cause-and-effect relationships: situation A and situation B. Three types differ from each other in causative semantic means of expression: 1) morphological (synthetic) causative, 2) lexical causative (in words: He killed him. Labor ennobles a person, 3) syntactic (analytical) causative.

The morphological mode of cause and effect arises by relative and productive means.

It is well known that the basis of the worldview is formed by the model that arises in the surrounding world, with which a person contacts, and in his thoughts. This model is conceptual. Each concept has a sign that is subject to change in consciousness. Including the causal concept. The causal concept arises on the basis of long-term human experience, is encoded by universal material means. Although the cause arises as an image, afterwards it is transformed into a sensitive image. For example: the image of "fear" can be for various reasons.

In general form, the causal concept in the Azerbaijani language is manifested in three ways: 1) notification (labeling); 2) expression (to express all the subtleties of the reason); 3) description (open in detail).

In the causal concept, there is evidence of mental thinking: an event, a condition; reason, instigator, culprit, pretext, basis. For example: Armenian vandalism is the cause of major tragedies. They have a reason. Why do we remember God in difficult times in our lives? Despite the fact that winter is very beautiful, we still bless spring. Due to the fact that grass grows in the gardens, the poor no longer depend on the Baku millionaires (J. Mammadguluzadeh).

These examples show that the causal concept acts as a structural and meaningful element of the personality's thinking system, and provides a process of information processing that reflects subjective human practice in accordance with certain categories and classes that have arisen in social existence.

Thus, the causal concept, being a complex semantic structure, is reflected through the semantic series of the language. The origin of these meanings (mentioned above) occurs in the context situation. The meanings included in this area are also explained at the level of a variety of social relations (cultural, self-knowledge, etc.).

Causal relations with the help of the phraseological expression "to serve as a cause" increase

emotions in colloquial and poetic speech, to a high degree reveal the assessment. For example:

The Lord God helped in recovery.

Once again the Most High would serve as a cause,

To see the arch at the white gorge.

Lean my face against rosy cheeks

To see black strands of hair

Sweat dripping from the chin. (G. Zakir)

Here the concept of cause becomes objective through expression. It is the expression "to cause" that is transferred as the value of the people.

As in other languages, in modern Azerbaijani language, causative constructions (reasons) are used a lot in literary texts. Causality, a causal relationship between events is a characteristic feature of such syntactic units. Grammatical constructions of reason arise in the replicas of question-and-answer of dialogue speech. The reasons for the events are asked, and their reasons are clarified in the answers.

"The essence of causality is in its compelling, prompting, encouraging, coercive, generative properties. Forms that combine these forms are causative" (4, p. 64-73).

Any text that has such forms is an object of serious study of the syntactic section of the language. Texts reflecting this form are perceived as a result of the creation of speech activity, written sources, the expediency of a speech work, accessibility. Again, texts of the same content in the process of speech are understood as a "model" that provides perception, determines the form of thought, thinking.

It is also clear that, according to the theory of the text, it is necessary to pay attention to a number of aspects of the language: the semantic side of the text - the process of formation, comprehension of meanings (for example, cause-and-effect meaning); perception; relevant communication units, creating favorable conditions for providing information content related to the cause.

In linguistic literature there is such an idea that texts expressing cause-and-effect relations are formed on the basis of 3 principles: 1) deixis (indication directly, by signs); 2) presupposition (knowledge about objective reality); 3) linguistic context (sequential construction of sentences) (5).

The causal concept is implemented in the text based on all three principles. The reasoning is directly based on the language context. Conjunctions *because*, *therefore*, *why*, *for a reason*, *etc.* act only directly in the process of indicating in the Azerbaijani language. According to the meaning, the listed conjunctions of cause used in the meaning of indication (marking) correspond to each other and this property performs a cataphoric function. Conjunction *because* acts as a synonym for conjunction *therefore* and forms cataphoric relations. In each case, the speaker and listener directly participate in the speech situation, that is, these conjunctions are used as deictic words. Each of these conjunctions can be used as synonym without significantly affecting the meaning. For example:

- They say Anar is not an irreplaceable person, I also agree with that. In general, there are no irreplaceable people. All can be replaced, but you have been looking for a replacement for 32 years already, you warned. Well, find it, why don't you find it? BECAUSE what one person wants, another group of people does not want. FOR THE SAME REASON, they say: let Anar stay! If a hundred people love me, then at least three are against me. Today the Union of Writers has 2,000 members. Out of 2000 members, 1900 are on my side. I was unanimously elected chairman at four congresses. Now if someone is against me, then it is quite natural. BECAUSE they have a desire. Someone wants a title, someone - a prize, someone - a pension ... Sometimes young people are confused. But I am glad that sooner or later young people will also see the light. At one time it was said that the flag would be planted in the Union of Writers. We'll get Anar out of there with an automatic machine. We didn't allow the Union of Writers to fall apart. THEREFORE, we should be grateful. If we weren't guarding, they would have sold everything here by room (Anar).

Najaf, Yes ... Well, I would say so ... Okay, and WHY are you so upset? Khanmurad. WHY WOULD I not be upset? This man and I are friends, we spent many days together. (Efendiev I. Selected works in 6 volumes, II volume, Baku, Writer, 1984.

In the process of their development, these conjunctions, along with the creation of syntactic

links between various information centers, realize, clarify and direct logical-semantic links. Causal conjunctions play a large role in the formation of the syntactic structure, information unit of a complex sentence and text components and turn into an element of their structure. Among the unused sides of the syntactic units of cause-and-effect conjunctions, in sentences created by special means (through conjunctions), it is impossible to notice a sufficient number of semantic features. For example:

- We are still friends with Elchin. Our relationship with Akram deteriorated later. I don't want to talk about Akram. BECAUSE, as soon as I say one phrase, Akram is immediately informed. Akram speaks, and then I have to answer. FOR THIS REASON, I will not talk about it. (Anar)

Thus, in the formation of predicative centers of the text, which carry the same semantic load as the causal information, the role of conjunctions *because, for this reason*, through which relationships are realized, is very great. The conjunctions in question in the text create relationships of predicative centers, which act as a connection between cause-semantic relationships.

A text is a piece of speech. In this passage, there are various speech means that generate the content of the cause. One of these means are conjunctions. These complex conjunctions express the content of the cause. The role of conjunctions in programming of various information and implementing various syntactic structures of causal relationships in a text is very large. From this point of view, different information can be found in the following two examples:

1. The student could not concentrate; something bothered him, dispelled his thoughts.
2. The student could not concentrate; because (due to the fact that) something bothered him, dispelled his thoughts.

The first clause is an explanatory related not complex clause, and the second is a complex clause with a subordinate clause of reason.

E. Hasanova describes her position to this issue in the following way: "Indeed, when there are no conjunctions, it is not easy to determine the semantic relationship of predicative centers. This leads to the fact that the conjunction plays an important role in the formation of such syntactic units and turns into a very important and indivisible part of the construction. The lack of conjunctions, in general, shows itself as a factor in speaking. Here the semantic relationship of the components, the main semantic accent is conveyed using intonation, gestures and facial expressions inherent in oral speech" (6, p. 22-23)

Directly, as a rule, the expression "for this reason" is widely used:

Suddenly Sultan Huseyn Baigara remembered something. Sultan was very touched of such a sincere attitude of Shah Khatai. And for this reason, he was very pleased to remember the past together with Khatai.

Thus, in the process of the research, the following scientific results were obtained:

Analysis of linguistic facts shows that in the formation and expression of the content of the cause in the components of the text, conjunctions *because, therefore, for this reason*, and others are widely used. These conjunctions in both complex and simple texts, connecting sentences with each other, are the main means of expressing the concept of cause. Through these conjunctions, a chain link arises in the sentences that form the cause of the text. Sentences composed with the help of conjunctions indicating the reason retain their independence to a certain extent outside the text, their meaning is realized not only in the text. In other words, conjunctions *because, therefore, for a reason, for that reason*, specifically, actively participate in the formation of the text. Just like a formal means.

It can be concluded that the use of these conjunctions is not limited to the above. They can manifest themselves at the end of the text as a means that generates an effect after a cause. But there is a change in the content. The communicative aspect is not so difficult, in some points the preference is given to the constructive meaning.

Such studies can be important from the point of view of obtaining generalized conclusions related to the study of the causative problem in relation to one language, and the syntactic and semantic structure of world languages, including Turkic. It also reveals the logical-grammatical, structural-semantic, communicative-functional and pragmatic properties of the causal concept.

THE MEANING AND PURPOSE OF THE STUDY. The research has both theoretical and practical significance. The theoretical significance of the study is presented as a form of manifestation of relations that give rise to a cause-and-effect concept, and, as a rule, present in the syntax, conceptology of Azerbaijani texts. The reason is that these relations, as a conceptual and categorical connection in the syntactic system of the language, have not been studied. In general, a serious attempt is made in the study to generalize the conceptual thoughts that differ from each other that arise when describing the theoretical problems of the cause-and-effect concept, and the information load of the concept of cause and effect is determined.

THE PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY lies in the fact that, affecting the syntax, linguoculturology of the text, being included in the program of universities and schools, it is relevant in this area and requires special attention. The results of the article allow us to give an even more systematized interpretation for teaching the courses "Modern Azerbaijani language", "Cultural linguistics" in the noted educational institutions.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY. Conceptual provisions relating to the syntax of the text, linguoculturology, and which are the aim of the study, can be the object of special courses and help in the improvement of the above subjects. The main goal is to determine the place and status of the notion of the cause-and-effect concept in the presentation of information in the textual syntax of the Azerbaijani language and to give their systematic characteristics.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. Speaking about research methods, first of all, it should be noted that the role of cause and effect as a universal connection in the process of cognition and expression in language is clarified using the method of traditional linguistic analysis.

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